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Internal Audit Departmental Attributes and Financial Reporting Quality of Public Sector Entities in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Internal audit is an important element of management of scarce resources that provides best advice and mechanisms to public sector managers to assist them to meet their responsibilities. The main objective of this study is to examine internal audit department and financial reporting quality in public sector entities in Anambra state. Specifically, the study determined the effect of internal audit department size on financial reporting quality of the public sector. Ascertain the effect of internal auditors' experience on financial reporting quality of the public sector. Examined the effect of internal auditors' expertise on financial reporting quality of public sector. Find out the effect of gender on financial reporting quality of public sector entity and determine the extent to which compliance with IPSAS affects financial reporting quality of public sector.. A sample of 8 core internal audit departments from public sector entities of Anambra State were used. The study employed ex-post facto and longitudinal research design. The descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis were analyzed using panel regression analysis. The result revealed that internal audit departmental size and internal auditors' expertise have a positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality which was statistically significant at 5% level of significance while internal auditor's compliance with IPSAS also showed a positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality of 8 core internal audit departments in Anambra State while internal auditors experience and gender documented a non-significant effect on financial reporting quality. The study recommends that public sector regulatory bodies should increase internal audit departmental size in order to have adequate members who can monitor financial reporting process in order to add value and improve reporting quality.

Keywords: Internal Audit, Financial Reporting Quality, Public Sector Entities, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The quality of financial reporting has been the focus over the past decade, and it will continue to be the primary focus in the future (Celina Tan & Muhammad Taufik. 2022; Kaawaase, Nairuba, Akankunda & Bananuka, 2021). An entity's responsibility is to prepare financial statements that reflect its financial condition (Alzoubi, 2014). Alzoubi (2014) argues that financial statements should always provide reliable information to assist users in making decisions. An essential aspect of reliability is the quality of the financial information, which plays a significant role in influencing users to reach decisions, and in evaluating corporate performance (Davis & Cestona, 2021).

The value of financial reports is determined by the quality of information it purports to communicate to users. Quality financial reporting increases in great measure, the confidence of investors and the general public in financial and non-financial information hence contributing to a country's economic growth and

financial stability. In the private sector, Quality financial reporting provides to stakeholders an accurate depiction of a company's finances, including their revenues, profits, expenses, capital, and cash flow, as formal records that provide in-depth insights into financial information. Likewise, in the Public sector, Quality financial reporting ensures proper accountability and transparency of public finances. Okere, Eluyela, Bassey, and Ajetunmobi, (2017), opined that proper transparency and accountability are possible because, quality financial reporting leads to better informed assessments of the resource allocation decisions made by governments. Thus the provision of information and disclosure of the activities and financial performance of the sector necessitated the demand for unbiased financial reporting, According to Izedonmi and Olateru- Olagbegi (2021), The increasingly and continuous demand for accountability and transparency in governance has actually brought about tremendous upsurge in the number, quality and sophistication of pecuniary reporting of government activities This is particularly important to citizens, who are taxed to fund public services. Hence, managers of the resources are expected to utilize the resources in their control in a manner that improves citizens' welfare and account for those resources by ensuring financial reporting that provides a background for people to have informed judgment on government performance and accountability. In the view of Tasios and Bekiaris, (2012), government financial reporting quality is of great importance to the society at large because of its impact on economic decisions. Consistent with this, (Izedomni & Ibadin, 2013 argued that strong and transparent financial reporting help in decision making and make governments to be more accountable to the public.

It is generally observed that proper accountability and transparency of public finances have ceased to exist. Safeguard of government resources against waste, fraud and inefficiency are seen to be things of the past. Due process in the collecting and spending of public funds in line with state laws and regulations are no longer determined. The Financial Accounting Standard Board (FASB), 2010; International Accounting Standard Board (IASB), 2008; International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB), 2014, stipulate, as objective of financial reporting, that financial reporting of public sector entities should provide information about an entities financial statement that is useful to the users for accountability and economic decisions. So the quality of the report depends on its ability to provide useful information that meets the qualitative characteristics of the information (IPSAS, 2010). Such qualities are, relevance, timeliness, understandability and comparability. These qualitative characteristics of financial statements have long been the focus of accounting standard setters (Agubata, 2019), because they make accounting information meaningful. Both IASB and IPSASB believe that high financial statement quality is achieved by adhering to the objective and qualitative characteristics of financial information (IASB, 2008, 2010; IPSASB, 2014).

Many governments world over advocate the need for good financial accountability and transparency to ensure there is public trust on the service delivery. However, the financial reporting practices in public sector have been challenged in many forums both intentionally and nationally because of the inadequacy of financial information reported in the financial statements. As a result, numerous reforms have taken place in the public sector, aimed at enhancing effectiveness and efficiency of delivery of public accounting and reporting system mostly prompted by economic globalization (Nistor, 2012; Andre, 2014). In recent years, most countries under the Organization of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) adopted reforms in the public accounting and reporting systems following the New Public Management (NPM) perspectives and principles. The main aim of the reforms was to improve public service management and to increase the transparency and accountability of governments (Caper-choice, 2006, Chan & Xiaoyue, 2002). Similarly, the introduction of International Public Sector Accounting Standards by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Boards was to address the quality of financial reporting with the intention of increasing public confidence in public sector financial management.

In addition to the above reforms, prior studies have contributed that financial reporting quality in the public sector can also be improved through the role of internal audit department (Tambingon, Yadiati, Kewo 2018), Okereson (2013), argues that the responsibilities for ensuring effective internal auditing normally, rests on the internal auditors. Thus, Internal audit provides reasonable assurance that there is effectiveness and efficiency of operations and internal controls, compliance with the set procedures and

adherence to rules and regulations of the entity. On the one hand, organizations that institute proper internal controls have been noted for presenting quality financial reports (Chebungwen & Kwasira, 2014). Audit committee helps public entities to improve the quality of financial reporting by ensuring that the management adhere to the procedures and regulations put in place. Therefore, in the light of the above assertions, this study is aimed at providing insight into the effect of internal audit on financial reporting quality of public sector entities in Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Many public sector entities in Nigeria in recent time have been observed with high incidence of fraud, misappropriation, misapplication of funds and poor operational efficiency. The truthfulness of the information disclosed by the financial reporting process in the public sector is indispensable, fraudulent Financial reporting practices, abnormal earnings management and all other forms of financial reporting malfeasances have greatly reduced investors' confidence in financial reports and its ability to perform its fundamental functions. (Ogoun & Perelayeta 2020) The high level of corruption in Nigeria today indicates that accountability is not going well. The condition of our governments tends to be inefficient and ineffective in governance. Despite the public entities relying on the government of Nigeria for their budgetary allocations, the level of accountability has been low coupled with numerous audit queries from the Office of Auditor General (OAG). According to Macharia (2014) the resources allocated to public entities are not put into proper use as the Auditor General reports for 2010/2011 to 2014/15 financial years showed a big gap between finances injected and financial reports utilization. Thus, Hamisi, (2012) argue that the government financial management system is not providing reliable financial information for decision making. Weak internal control and poor financial reports have made public entities provide financial information which are insufficient to hold management accountable (Kiilu & Ngugi, 2014). Such extensive failure in the financial disclosure has generated the demand by regulators and other stakeholders for a quality financial information and to reinforce the control of managers by putting up adequate governance structures (Klai & Omri, 2011).

A number of studies done on the financial reporting including, Ball and Plugrath (2012) who stated that consistent and appropriate use of IPSAS provide high quality information that enhances comparability in financial reporting while Chinedu et al (2016) focused on the adoption and implementation of IPSASs in the public sector entities in Nigeria with special emphasis on training of government auditors and corruption reduction. Despite the importance of public sector financial reporting quality requirement by Public Financial Management (PFM) Act (2012) there is limited research on the factors influencing financial reporting quality in the Nigerian public sector since the majority of studies done earlier had focused on financial reporting and financial regulations in the private sector entities hence creating a knowledge gap. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the effect of internal audit on financial reporting quality of public sector entities in Nigeria. Against this backdrop, the following objectives were set to guide this study as follows:

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Framework

Financial Reporting Quality

Financial reporting within the context of public sector is a process of collecting, classifying, summarizing, and reporting accounting information that relates to government activities so as to allow citizen participation and holding elected officials accountable (Bastani *et al.*, 2012). It provides background for people to have informed judgment on government performance and accountability assessment (Bastani *et al.*, 2012). Financial reporting is the process by which corporate entities provide interested parties (users) with information on their transactions during an accounting period (Mbobo & Ekpo, 2016). Financial reporting is one of the major means that corporate management uses in communicating financial information for a given period. In this regard, the International Accounting Standard (IAS 1) states that the purpose of financial reporting is to provide information about the financial position, financial performance and cash flows of an entity that is useful to a wide range of users in making economic decisions. Such information is communicated through financial statements. Kabiru and Usman (2021)

quoting Ibadin and Dabor (2015) stated that financial statements show the results of the management's stewardship of the resources entrusted to it by revealing economic information on assets, liabilities, equity, income and expenses, including gains and losses; contributions by and distributions to owners in their capacity as owners; and cash flows. Such information, along with other information in the notes, assists users of financial statements in predicting the entity's future cash flows and, in particular, their timing and certainty. Therefore, accounting information contained in the financial statements is one of the very essential information needed by various stakeholders especially investors for making informed economic decisions. Investors in search of investment avenues use the accounting information contained in the financial statements of the intended investing company in pricing of shares. Market participants seek high-quality financial reporting or information to mitigate the information asymmetry as such quality information should be a pre-requisite for well a functioning capital market. Thus, companies that provide high-quality information have an added advantage in their rating in the capital market. The increasing demand for quality financial reporting creates the need for effective and efficient monitoring mechanisms. This is necessitated by the conflict of interest between managers, who serve as agents and resource holders, who serve as principals, wherein, managers carry out activities that are counter-productive in the realization of the interests of resource holders. Therefore, board of directors is instituted to monitor the activities of managers. The board sets several monitoring measures that will ensure the integrity of management's decision.

Internal audit

According to Cohen and Sayag (2010), internal audit is those audit that being carried out by employees within an enterprise. It also an independent appraisal functions established by the management of an organisation for the review of the internal control system as a service to the organisation. It objectively examines, evaluates and report on the adequacy of internal control as a contribution to the proper economic, efficient and effective use of resources. The head of internal audit department normally report to the highest authority within the enterprises in order to be independent of members of staff. The audit approach under this type of audit is continues audit approach which involves examination of transaction and balances, throughout the accounting period without auditing to a specific date. According to Millichamp (2000), internal audit is viewed as an independent appraisal function established within an organization to examine and evaluate the activities of an organization as a service to the organization. It is also a process generally

Internal auditors are appointed by the management of the organization to examine and evaluate the effectiveness and soundness of financial administrative activities as well as procedure put in place. They are essentially regarded as the watchdog of management. They monitor, examine and ensure adherence to management operational policies and guidelines. They evaluate the effectiveness of the system of internal control and check. The internal auditors therefore require competence and time to review the system of control in force. According to Pickett (2010) Competency is internal auditors apply the knowledge, skills, and experience needed in the performance of internal audit service.

Theoretical Review

The theoretical framework gives the meaning of a word in terms of the theories on internal audit relationship and financial reporting quality. It assumes both knowledge and acceptance of the theories that this research work depends upon. Under this theoretical frame work, there are many relevant theories that can be used to explain the relationship between internal audit and financial reporting quality but we discussed only three theories that best explained our work and anchored our work on it. On this note stewardship theory, stakeholder's theory and agency theory were discussed and it was on these theories that we anchored our work on. These theories also help to discuss the effect of internal audit on financial reporting quality of public entities in Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Susant and Rimbano (2022) aims to examine the factors that influence the quality of the Local Government Finance of the Government of Musirawas, South Sumatera, Indonesia. The authors used 110 persons from the government apparatus who represent their working unit of the Finance Management in the Government of Mursirawas, South Sumatera, Indonesia as their respondents. The research utilizes a

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) method. The research results showed that the Performance quality of the LAPD in the Government of Musirawas, South Sumatra, Indonesia, is simultaneously influenced by the competency of the Apparatus human resources, motivation, and the local accounting system; partially, it was influenced by the apparatus human resource competency.

In a most recent study done by Agyei-Mensah (2022), He investigates impact of audit committee attributes on financial reporting quality and timeliness of listed firms in Ghana. The study uses 90 firm-year observations for the period 2013-2015 for firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange. A descriptive analysis was performed to provide the background statistics of the variables examined. This was followed by regression analysis, which forms the main data analysis. The descriptive statistics indicate that over the four years, the mean value of financial reporting quality is 42% and timeliness of financial reporting is 86 days. The regression analysis results indicate that: financial reporting quality has a statistically positive relationship with audit committee financial expertise and size; audit report lag has a statistically negative relationship with audit committee financial expertise and audit committee independence. This study is one of the few to measure the influence of audit committee characteristics on financial reporting quality and timeliness in Sub-Saharan Africa.

In the same vein, Ehigie and Isenmilia (2022) examined conceptually the relevance of the audit committee financial expertise to financial reporting timeliness of a firm. The methodology adopted in this study is library research whereby relevant and extant literature related to the audit committee financial expertise and financial reporting timeliness. Audit committee financial expertise was x-ray from the perspective of accounting financial expertise and the non-accounting financial expertise. Observations from the study highlights that the presence of accounting financial experts in an audit committee is an important element that mitigate reportorial challenges and motivates financial reporting timeliness. The study recommends that financial experts in the audit committee should be given more power to enable them discharge their duty effectively and efficiently, the definition of audit committee financial expertise should not relegate other relevant profession to the background, and the impact of the audit committee financial expertise on audit expectation gap should be considered when appointing members of the audit committee.

Hariani (2021) aims to examine the determinants of Financial Reporting Quality (FRQ). An empirical study was conducted across local governments in Indonesia to test the hypothesis. In the study, 302 qualified questionnaires were collected from local government employees through self-administered surveys. Furthermore, the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) technique was used for data analysis. The result showed that Internal Control System (ICS), Effective Information Technology Governance (ITG), Regulation on Performance Measurement (RPM), and Political Influence (PIN), as well as Transparency (TRS), have a relationship with FRQ. Meanwhile, the hypothesis that Commitment to Organization (COR) strengthens the effect of ICS, ITG on FRQ was rejected. The result provided evidence of the significant indirect effect of RPM and PIN on FRQ through TRS. In conclusion, FRQ, as the result of accounting activities, provided financial information understood by users and used for decision-making in the future.

Isughayer, (2021), conducted an investigation on the impact of auditor's competency, integrity, and ethics on audit quality from the perceptions of auditors. The data is collected through questionnaires distributed to auditors in auditing firms in Saudi Arabia. The sample used was amounted to 102 auditors. The study surveyed different external auditors to explore their audit process attributes for achieving quality of audit. The findings show that the attributes of competence, integrity, and ethics have significant impact on audit quality. The findings indicate that the most important elements of attributes affecting audit quality are auditors' continuous improvement and training programs, ways of carrying out their duties, and their compliance to code of conduct. This study extends the literature on audit quality and provides useful insights for audit firms and professional bodies for the policies and producers to be adopted and implemented to enhance audit quality

Omorieg and Eromosele (2020) examined some factors affecting financial reporting quality in the Nigeria public sector using one hundred and fifty (150) copies of likert-scale questionnaire comprising fifteen questions (with three questions representing financial reporting quality and three questions

representing each of the four explanatory variables) which were administered to civil servants, members of civil society organizations, legal practitioners, academics, and professional accountants in office of the auditor general of the federation. The estimation of the responses of ninety-five (95) useable retrieved questionnaire done with the aid of ordinary least square regression techniques shows that internal control has a significant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; Public account committee effectiveness has a significant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; Stringent penalty for financial misconduct has an insignificant negative relationship with financial reporting quality; and Adoption of IPSAS has a significant positive relationship with financial reporting quality in Nigeria public sector. The authors recommended that public sector accounting set-up in Nigeria should include efficient and effective internal control mechanism, functional public account committee and incorporation of IPSAS requirements into the financial statements reporting framework.

Rakhman and Wijayana (2019) investigates the determinants of FRQ in the public sector. They use the type of audit opinion as a proxy for reporting quality, with an unqualified opinion representing the best reporting quality while a disclaimer of opinion represents the worst quality. Using manually collected data from 3018 financial reports of local governments in Indonesia from 2008 to 2014, they find that a high proportion of capital expenditures in the total budget is associated with low FRQ. Further, they find that larger and wealthier local governments are associated with higher FRQ. Finally, they find that local governments under more experienced mayors have higher reporting quality. They conclude that certain characteristics of local governments and of mayors are associated with the types of audit opinion and that financial incentives accelerate the improvement of reporting quality.

Muraina and Dandago (2019) examine the effects of the implementation of the International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) on Nigeria's financial reporting quality. The study employed a survey research design to determine the effects of the implementation of the IPSAS on Nigeria's financial reporting quality. Partial Least Square 3(SmartPLS 3) technique of analysis was applied to achieve the research objective. The study found that accountability positively and significantly affects the quality of financial reporting in Nigeria. Specifically, IPSAS has improved the level of accountability, which in turn improved Nigeria's financial reporting quality. IPSAS-Accrual has engendered the Nigerian Government to launch the Asset Tracking and Management Project (ATM-Project) in order to easily track its assets for the purpose of accountability. Thus, accountability was discovered in this study to be the most essential factor to enhance the quality of financial reporting using accrual based IPSAS in Nigeria.

Furqan, Wardhani, Martani, and Setyaningrum (2019) aims to analyze the effect of audit findings and audit recommendations follow-up on the quality of financial reports and the quality of public services in the context of applying accrual accounting systems to local government in Indonesia. The study also examines whether the quality of the financial report affects the quality of public services. This study employed cross-sectional regression using data from 1,437 observations from 491 districts/cities for 2014–2016. The data illustrates the conditions prior to the adoption of the accrual accounting system (2014), the initial year of application/transition period (2015) and the second year of the expected accrual accounting system (2016). The results of the study indicate that, in general, the quality of financial reports affects the quality of public services. Regarding the implementation of audits in the public sector, it is also found that audit findings have a negative impact on the quality of financial report and the quality of public services, while audit recommendations follow-up plays a positive role in improving the quality of financial report and the quality of public services.

Gap in knowledge

Our gap in literature is based on area of coverage, period covered and introduction of new variables. Therefore, the research gaps in the empirical literature are viewed under the following sub-heading.

Geographical and Sector Gap: Literature on internal audit department and financial reporting quality of public sector entities is scanty as most studies either focused on developed countries or even on audit committee alone but none of them studied all public sector entities within the internal audit department in Nigeria at the same time.

Variable and Periodic Gap: The uniqueness of this research over other prior studies is the addition of three new variables to the model we adopted. To the best of researchers' knowledge, there is no

indigenous study that has used internal auditors expertise, internal auditors experience and internal auditors compliance to IPSAS to proxy internal audit department with reference to financial reporting quality. Therefore, we introduced these three variables to identify and measure the effect of internal audit department on financial reporting quality using all public sector entities in Anambra State. We are very sure of this gap so we decided to fill it. Besides, majority of these scholars used internal auditors age, tenure, nationality and female gender but this study used internal auditor’s expertise, internal auditors experience and internal auditors compliance to IPSAS in addition to the previously used ones by prior studies and extended the study for a very long period of time (10years) spanning from 2013 to 2022. Moreover, there is no indigenous study that has used internal auditor’s expertise, internal auditors experience and internal auditors compliance to IPSAS to proxy internal audit department. In light of this backdrop, this study intends to fill existing gap by assessing the effect of internal audit department on financial reporting quality of public sector entities in Nigeria. This is the knowledge gap this study intends to address therefore contributing to the existing literature.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design to be adopted in this study is the *ex post facto* research design. This study covered all the internal audit departments in public sector entities in Anambra State within the period of ten years from 2012 to 2021. The secondary data that was collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation, variance inflation factor and regression analysis

Table 2 Operationalization of Variables

<i>Dependent Variable</i> Financial Reporting Quality (FREQTY)	<i>Estimated using market based variable like Timeliness (Inspirations were drawn from prior studies of Francis, LaFond, Olsson & Schipper, 2004). Timeliness of financial report measured as the time interval between the end of the reporting period and the date the financial statements are issued. ie No of days between the financial year ended and the date of auditor’s report.</i>
<i>Internal Audit Department Size</i> (IADSZ)	<i>Total number of internal audit department staff</i>
<i>Internal Auditor’s Experience</i> (IADEXP)	<i>We measure Internal Auditors experience using a dummy variable equal to one (1) if the internal auditor was employed by the department prior to becoming Internal auditor, and zero if otherwise.</i>
<i>Internal Auditor’s Expertise</i> (IADEPZ)	<i>Internal Auditor with finance or accounting expertise or membership in any professional accounting bodies measured as a dummy variable 1 if the internal auditor is an expert and a member of any professional accounting bodies and 0 if otherwise.</i>
<i>Gender (GEND)</i>	<i>Gender was measured as a dummy variable 1 if the internal Auditor is a female and zero if otherwise.</i>
<i>Compliance with IPSAS (CIPSAS)</i>	<i>Measured as a dummy variable where "1" is assigned to the internal audit department in a year with full sections in annual reports with notes on how they have complied with IPSAS adoption and "0" otherwise</i>

Source: Researchers’ compilation (2026)

Model Specification:

The model for this study will be adopted from the work of Omoregie and Eromosele (2020) which is stated functionally as FRQ = (PACE, SPFM, ADIPSAS) this model will be modified to suit the variables used in this study. Hence the model for the study will be based on the variables used in this study. This model therefore modifies and extends the model tested by prior studies and panel regression analysis will be adopted for the purpose of hypothesis testing and will be guided by the following functional linear model:

$$FREQTY = f(IADSZ, IADEXP, IADEPZ, GEND, COMPSA)$$

This can be mathematically expressed as follows.

$$FREQTY_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 IADSZ_{it} + \beta_2 IADEXP_{it} + \beta_3 IADEPZ_{it} + \beta_4 GEND_{it} + \beta_5 COMPSA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots 1$$

Where:

FREQTY stands for Financial Reporting Quality
 IADSZ connotes Internal Audit Departmental Size
 IADEXP means Internal Auditors Experience
 IADEPZ stands for Internal Auditors Expertise
 GEND means Gender

ϵ_{it} = Radom error term or stochastic variables of the model capturing other unexplanatory variables.

Subscripts i denote number of departments, t denotes years or time-series dimensions ranging from 2012-2021, and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5$, Stands for Regression model coefficients

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics Analysis

The aim of the descriptive statistics was to describe the general distributional properties of the data, to identify any unusual observations or any unusual patterns of observations that may cause problems for later analyses to be carried out on the data. Thus, initial exploration of the data using simple descriptive tools was provided to describe and summarize the data generated for the study. The detailed result of the descriptive statistics was presented in table 1 under the appendix. The Table below shows the descriptive statistics of the internal audit departments that make up our sample.

Pearson Correlation Matrix

Pearson’s correlation matrix was applied to check the degree of association between internal audit departmental characteristics and financial reporting quality so as to determine the nature or degree of association i.e. positive or negative correlation and the magnitude of the correlation between dependent variable (financial reporting quality) and independent variables with other explanatory variables. Correlation coefficient measures the direction and degree of association between two or more variables. It is worthy to note at this point that correlation measures association not causality. Correlation can be positive (>0) or negative (<0). A positive correlation means that two variables move in the same direction while a negative correlation means they move in opposite direction. Therefore, in examining the association among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in the table 2 below.

	FREQTY	IADSZ	IADEXP	IADEPZ	IADGEN	COMPSA
FREQTY	1.000000					
IADSZ	0.035752	1.000000				
IADEXP	0.177722	0.018445	1.000000			
IADEPZ	-0.083197	0.262548	-0.127386	1.000000		
IADGEN	0.054048	-0.028639	0.022272	0.096462	1.000000	
COMPSA	-0.525747	0.285002	-0.336910	0.215238	0.016371	1.000000

Source: researcher’s summary of correlation result (2023) using E-view 12

The result of the correlation coefficient showed mixed correlation. This association identified buttresses the point that our variables have a linear relationship. Furthermore, the strength of the relationship between variables measured by the Pearson product-moment correlation showed that the association between the variables is relatively small and was below the threshold of 0.80, suggesting the absence of the problem of multicollinearity in the predictor variables. In this section we present and discuss the Pairwise correlations among the variables of internal audit departmental attributes and financial reporting reporting. Table 4.2.3 shows that most of the correlation coefficients between the study’s variables are relatively low, nevertheless there are still some relatively high correlations between some of those variables. The above results show that there exists a positive and a very weak association between financial reporting quality, internal audit departmental size and internal auditor gender diversity (FREQTY/IADSZ and IADGEN = 0.035 and 0.054) respectively. It was discovered that a negative and very weak association exists between financial reporting quality and internal auditor’s expertise (FREQTY and IADEPZ = -0.0831) while a negative but very strong relationship exists between financial

reporting quality and compliance with IPSAS (FREPTY and COMPSA = -0.525). This strongly proves that compliance with IPSAS will go a long way in improving financial reporting quality of public sector entities.

Going by the association between other explanatory variables, we discovered that there exists a direct and positive relationship between internal audit departmental size and other explanatory variables except with internal auditor's gender diversity that recorded an inverse relationship with departmental size. In the same vein, internal auditor expertise recorded a direct correlation with all other explanatory variables while internal auditor experience documented a positive but very weak association with internal auditor's gender (IADEXP and IADGEN = 0.0222). Similarly, internal auditor experience had a negative but strong association with internal auditor expertise and compliance with IPSAS (IADEXP/IADEPZ and COMPSA = -0.127 and -0.336). Therefore, in checking for multi-collinearity, the study noticed from the correlation table that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This indicates the absence of multi-collinearity problem in the model used for the analysis. This correlation matrix will not serve as a basis for generalization on the actual relationship between internal audit departmental characteristics and financial reporting quality as correlation matrix only gives a mere degree of relationship between the dependent and the independent variables themselves, This also justifies the use of the panel least regression.

Regression Analysis

In order to examine the relationship that exists between the dependent variable (FREPTY) and the independent variables internal audit departmental attributes (IADSZ, IADEXP, IADEPZ, IADGEN, and COMPSA) and to test the formulated hypotheses, the study used the multiple regression analysis techniques. Therefore, in order to examine the responsiveness between dependent variable (FREPTY) and internal audit departmental attributes such as internal audit departmental size (IADSZ), internal auditor experience (IADEXP), internal auditor expertise (IADEXP), internal auditor gender diversity (IADGEN), and compliance with IPSAS (COMPSA) and to test the formulated hypotheses, we employed panel regression analysis since the data had both time series (2012-2021) and longitudinal properties (8 accredited internal audit departments). However, the study takes into cognizance the non homogeneity nature of the departments, hence the need for testing its effect on the data. This necessitates the use of hausman effect test to ascertain which effect to explain. Below is the summary of the Hausman test result in table2:

Hausman Effect Test

The summary result of regression analysis is presented below. However, the study takes into cognizance the non homogeneity nature of the public sector entities, hence the need for testing its effect on the data. This necessitated the use of Hausman effect test to ascertain which effect to explain. That is whether fixed effect or random effect is to be used in interpreting the regression result or to ascertain that which is best to be adopted in the study since our data is a panel data with complete information.

Hausman Effect Test: Decision rule

H_0 – random effect is more preferable than fixed effect

H_1 – fixed effect is more preferable to random effect

When chi-square probability value is less than 5% – rejects H_0 and accepts H_1 ($P \leq 0.05$)

When chi-square probability value is greater than 5% – accepts H_0 and rejects H_1 . ($P \geq 0.05$)

Hausman test is used to decide between fixed effect model or random effect model. When the Chi square (Prob) value is greater than 5%, you interpret random effect and said that random effect is more preferred to fixed effect but when it is less than 5%, you interpret fixed effect and said that fixed effect is more preferred to random effect. Below is the summary of the Hausman test result, details of the result was presented in table 4 under the appendix.

Table 3. Hausman Effect Tests

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test
Equation: Untitled
Test cross-section random effects

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	0.799847	5	0.9770

Source: Researcher’s summary of Hausman effect tests result (2026)

The Hausman test result above shows a chi-square statistics value of 0.7998 and probability value of 0.9770, this means that there is no homogeneity in the collection of the internal audit departmental data. Since the Chi-square (Prob) value is more than 5%, hence we accept the random effect and interpret its regression while the fixed effect is rejected. Hausman test shows that the random-effects estimation (REM) method is more appropriate than the fixed effects (FEM) for all the internal audit department of public sector entities in Anambra State; hence the results from REM is presented and interpreted. Therefore, the study used the random effect to correct the problem of heterogeneity in the data used for the study; the random effect regression result is presented in table 4 below.

Table 4: Random Effects Regression Result

Cross-section random effects test equation:
Dependent Variable: FREQTY
Method: Panel Least Squares
Date: 01/21/26 Time: 03:32
Sample: 2015 2024
Periods included: 10
Cross-sections included: 8
Total panel (balanced) observations: 80

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	197.6409	35.85778	5.511800	0.0000
IADSZ	3.581836	1.689551	2.119993	0.0377
IADEXP	-5.098750	21.44495	-0.237760	0.8128
IADEPZ	4.360801	40.27493	2.108276	0.0141
IADGEN	14.95924	19.81885	0.754799	0.4530
COMPSA	105.6666	21.09492	5.009105	0.0000

Effects Specification

Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)

Root MSE	70.66807	R-squared	0.327896
Mean dependent var	214.8000	Adjusted R-squared	0.207519
S.D. dependent var	86.74339	S.E. of regression	77.22018
Akaike info criterion	11.67886	Sum squared resid	399518.0
Schwarz criterion	12.06594	Log likelihood	-454.1546
Hannan-Quinn criter.	11.83406	F-statistic	2.723911
Durbin-Watson stat	1.766560	Prob(F-statistic)	0.004655

Source: Researchers’ Random Regression result (2026) from Eview 12

The table 4 above shows the panel regression analysis of 8 internal audit departments of public sector entities in Anambra State. From the table above, the F-statistics value of 2.723 and their P-value of 0.0046 showed that the overall regression analysis of our variables in the regression model was generally significant at 1% level of significance and it shows that the model was well specified in explaining financial reporting quality of 8 internal audit departments of public sector entities in Anambra State. From the result above, the study observed that the R. squared value was 0.327 (33%) approximately and R-squared adjusted value was 0.207 (21%) approximately. The value of R-squared which is the coefficient of determination stood at 33% which implies that 33% of the systematic variations in individual dependent variables were explained in the model while about 67% were unexplained thereby captured by the stochastic error term. Again, the adjusted R-squared which stood at 21% approximately indicates that all the independent variables jointly explain about 21% of the system variation in financial reporting quality of our sampled departments in over the 10years period while about 79% of the total variations were unaccounted for, hence captured by the stochastic error term. This reveals that about 33% quality in financial report can be attributable to the internal audit departmental attributes selected for the study while about 67% were unexplained thus captured by other factors that are likely to improve reporting quality but were not included in the model. Moreover, the F-statistics value of 2.723 and its probability value of 0.0046 shows that the financial reporting quality model used for the analysis were statistically significant at 1% level. This confirms the appropriateness of our model used for the analysis. The Durbin Watson statistics value of 1.7665 showed that the model is well spread since the value is approximately 2 and that there have not been self or auto correlation problem and that error are independent of each other.

CONCLUSION

An efficient and effective public sector entities need a transparent financial reporting system to boost investors' confidence in making investment decisions. The financial information should be of higher quality before it is delivered to outside stakeholders because users of financial information demand for complete, transparent and timely information. Thus, timely financial reporting is considered as one of the qualities of financial reporting that leads to quality decision making. This study has empirically provided evidence on the degree of relationship between internal audit departmental attributes proxy by internal audit departmental size, internal auditor's experience, internal auditor's financial expertise, internal auditor's gender diversity and compliance with IPSAS. Financial reporting quality which represents our dependent variable was proxied using timeliness of financial report of internal audit departments in Anambra State.

The findings from the study showed that internal audit departmental size, expertise and compliance with IPSAS has positive and significant effect on financial reporting quality. This implies that internal audit departmental size, auditor's expertise and compliance with IPSAS enhances financial reporting quality of the sampled departments. The implication is that further increase in number of members of internal audit staff with diverse accounting and financial qualification will result in high financial reporting quality. The finding is in line with the tenets of stewardship and agency theory which posit that Agency problem usually arise because the actions of managers which are not always in the best interest of the financiers, some of their actions are very detrimental to the fortunes of the financiers. As a result of the interest managers who are self-opportunistic, self-interested, there was an agency loss which is the extent to which returns to the residual claimants, the owners fall below what they would be if the owners, exercised direct control over the company (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The remedies to this conception of the agency problem within corporate governance involves the acceptance of certain 'agency costs' involved either in creating incentives or sanctions that will align executive self-interest with the interest of shareholders, or incurred in monitoring executive conduct in order to constrain their opportunism (Roberts, 2004). Thus principles of corporate governance are meant to control the internal and external entrenchment practices of executives through internal and external control mechanisms which either align the interest of executives with the government or monitor them directly. It is worthy to note that meeting the basic minimum standards of effectiveness through compliance with IPSAS ensure internal audit departments' efficiency in enhancing financial reporting quality. In conclusion, internal audit

departmental attributes have been empirically established by this study as a viable tool for improving public sector entities financial reporting quality.

Consequently, based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. First, the study reveals that the presence of additional one internal auditor with financial background is enough in enhancing the quality of financial reporting. Also, the regulatory bodies should strengthen their enforcement and compliance with code of public sector such as IPSAS, in order to ensure that the codes are effective and not just a mere document draft for the administrative purpose so as to give effect to investor protection and confidence. They should also impose sanction for non-compliance among firms. Hence, we recommend that the entire legal and regulatory framework together with the necessary institutional and environmental architecture for proper constitution and operation of an efficient internal audit departments should be over hauled and maintained at all times to enhance and improve financial reporting quality of selected internal audit departments in Nigeria. Moreover, public sector codes and regulation should be improved in order to strengthen financial reporting quality in the selected departments.

Public Implication

Amongst the recommendations is that public sector regulatory bodies should increase internal audit departmental size in order to have adequate members who can monitor financial reporting process in order to add value and improve reporting quality. Appointment of internal auditors based on past experience should be discouraged for all public sector entities in Anambra State since it was shown to have a negative and insignificant effect on financial reporting quality. The study also recommends that internal auditors financial expertise should be that of diversified nature to accommodate people with indebt knowledge on finance and accounting related matters and those with professional qualifications to improve financial reporting quality of public sector entities in Anambra State.

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